

2022, vol. 9, issue 1, 239-244

RESEARCH ARTICLE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6795800>

Student's motivation and satisfaction in watching intensity of variety show and reality show Transtv (uses and gratification theory analysis)

Ayu FEBRIYANTI, State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan, Indonesia

Elsa TIARA, State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan, Indonesia

Teddy DYATMIKA, State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan, Indonesia

M. Rikzam KAMAL, State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan, Indonesia

Aris PRIYANTO, State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan, Indonesia

Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the motives and satisfaction of students in the intensity of watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv, where Transtv is one of the television stations that broadcasts a lot of variety shows and reality shows. Several variety shows and reality shows on Transtv have even been reprimanded by KPI several times. However, there are still a lot of people watching these events. The purpose of this study is to examine a use of media and its underlying relationship from the point of view of the uses and gratification theory. The uses and gratification theory assumes that mass media does not have the power to influence audiences, but audiences use mass media based on their respective needs and needs. An explanatory quantitative approach is used in this study with the aim of explaining a measurable social phenomenon. The results of the correlation test findings in this study explain that the entertainment satisfaction obtained by respondents is influenced by motivation and intensity in watching variety shows and reality shows on TransTV through television media.

Keywords: Motive, Satisfaction, Intensity, Variety Show, Reality Show.

Introduction

Mass media is one thing that is very important in human life because humans are creatures who have a high curiosity, and this mass media as a means of delivering information to the public or the public (Yakunin et al., 2021). In fact, this is the main function of the mass media, namely the dissemination of information or commonly called the informative function (Bidzilya et al., 2021). From the informative function of the mass media, it makes the public or the public know about the events or events around it. Not only that, the mass media is also a means to develop culture, not only culture in terms of art and symbols, but also in terms of developing procedures, modes, lifestyles, and norms.

The mass media also plays a role in education (Sukardi, 2016). Mass media can provide education to everyone, regardless of gender, age, culture, social status, and so on, either directly or indirectly through various forms of content. In addition, mass media is also a means of entertainment for the community so that it can help reduce stress or tension. One of the mass media that presents a variety of entertainment content is television (M et al., 2018). Television is one of the most attractive mass

media because it is in the form of audio-visual (Farmer, 2016). Due to its audio-visual nature, television can present various programs, including variety shows and reality shows.

A variety show program is a television program that combines various types of entertainment, television stages such as comedy, song and drama. Meanwhile, reality show in terms means a show that is real (real), not engineered, not made up (Kwon et al., 2020). The events are taken from everyday life, people's lives as they are, namely the reality of society. Reality shows depict scenes as if they really took place without a scenario with the general audience being the general public instead of the cast (Roberts & De Benedictis, 2021). Various programs and reality shows are in great demand in all circles, including students (Campo-Prieto et al., 2021).

There are a lot of interest in variety shows and reality shows because: 1) dramas in these shows are close to everyday life, especially reality shows; 2) the storyline is easy to stir emotions; 3) simple ideas wrapped in extraordinary looks; 4) society needs entertainment according to reality; and 5) the presentation is attractive (Lu & Lu, 2022). Because the program was in great demand by the public, many television stations broadcast these programs (Woo & Khoo, 2020). One of the television stations that show a lot of variety shows and reality shows is Transtv. The events were the Bosque Family, the Holy Promise of Rafi and Gigi, Hangout with Andre Taulany, Mrs. Boss, Diary The Onsu, Rafi Billy And Friends, Nih Kita Kepo, Fortune Orang Sholeh, Sule Love Story, Safana, Brownis, Rumpi (No. Secret), Early Mornings, Viral Coffee, Original Chat, Uwu Moment, and so on.

Although these programs are in high demand and the scenes that are shown depict scenes that seem to take place without a script, in fact many scenes have been set from the start (Dixon et al., 2021). These programs also highlight a lot of the artist's life, and also feature scenes that are inappropriate and harmful to the audience (Makarov et al., 2022). There was even an event that was sanctioned by the KPI, namely "Morning Ambyaaarr". The Indonesian Broadcasting Commission (KPI) (Fardiah et al., 2020) gave administrative sanctions a written warning for the program for violating the 2012 KPI Broadcasting Code of Conduct and Broadcast Program Standards (P3SPS). This scene has ignored 8 (eight) articles in the P3SPS KPI.

Apart from not paying attention to aspects of child and adolescent protection. The scene is considered to heed the norms of decency and decency (Wuethrich et al., 2018). Moreover, variety shows often broadcast it live or live so that it cannot be predicted, edited, or cut (Prati, 2020). So that the audience can witness it directly. This causes the opportunity for the audience to imitate it is increasing. The mass media should be able to provide information and educate the public, but in reality they display inappropriate things and even violate the rules (Kuzina, 2020).

Although many variety shows and reality shows show scenes that are not useful, there are still many who watch the program, including students (Chen & Liu, 2021). This is of course based on the desire of the audience, in this case students, to watch the event. The existence of this desire can not be separated from the underlying motives. From the desire that is fulfilled it will be achieved a satisfaction. Media audiences are motivated by their needs and choose media types to satisfy their needs. Media use can be measured through the individual's relationship with the media, the type of media, and the amount of time measured using intensity (Littlejohn et al., 2017).

A theory of mass communication that uses and gratification emphasizes that the audience plays an active role in choosing which media to choose to meet their needs (Publication, 2021). Based on the brief description that has been presented, the author conducted a study on the motives and satisfaction of students in watching variety shows and reality shows based on the uses and gratification theory point of view.

Entertainment Motive

The indicator of entertainment motives in this variable is reduced to three questions to see the motives of entertainment desired by respondents when watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv through television mass media. The results can be seen in the following table:

Table 1. Do you focus on watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv to the end?

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Never focus	8	16
Rarely focus	20	40
Sometimes focus	21	42
Always focus	1	2
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary data processed by researchers, 2021

Based on the table above, students' responses to the question of whether to focus on watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv until the end were dominated by the "occasionally focused" attitude and had a difference of 2% higher than the "rarely focused" attitude. This explains that the level of focus of respondents in watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv through television media is not always focused on following the course of the event. This means that the respondent's condition while watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv through television media is followed by other activities.

Table 2. Is it changing to another channel when variety shows and reality shows on Transtv are in progress?

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Always changing channels	9	18
Sometimes changing channel	36	72
Rarely change channel	5	10
Never switch channel	-	-
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary data processed by researchers, 2021

The data above explains that there are no respondents who have never switched channels when watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv through television media. All respondents have switched to another channel when watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv. However, 72% of respondents stated that they "sometimes switch channels". Sometimes it means sometimes, once in a while. This means that respondents are quite consistent in watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv.

Table 3. Is watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv while doing other work?

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Always while doing other work	10	20
Sometimes while doing other work	26	52
Rarely while doing other work	12	24
Never while doing other work	2	4
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary data processed by researchers, 2021

Most of the respondents while watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv through television are not doing other jobs, respondents tend to focus on just watching. This is indicated by the respondent's attitude which is dominated by the attitude of "sometimes and rarely".

Entertainment Satisfaction

The entertainment satisfaction indicator in this variable consists of three statements originating from the motives of integration and social interaction.

Table 4. Can watching variety shows and reality shows on Trans Tv get entertainment?

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Do not get	2	4
Less get	5	10
Just get	41	82
Really get	2	4
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary data processed by researchers, 2021

Based on the table above, it can be seen that 82% of respondents chose the “enough to get” category from the question of whether watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv can get entertainment. Sufficient in this case implies that variety shows and reality shows on Transtv can meet the needs or satisfy the respondent’s desire to be able to get entertainment.

Table 5. Can watching variety shows and reality shows on Trans Tv get rid of boredom?

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Do not get	6	12
Less get	8	16
Just get	35	70
Really get	1	2
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary data processed by researchers, 2021

Most of the respondents were able to get rid of boredom while watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv. This can be seen from the percentage of the “enough to get” category, which is 70%, the highest among other categories.

Table 6. Can watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv get rid of problems?

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Do not get	18	36
Less get	16	32
Just get	15	30
Really get	1	2
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary data processed by researchers, 2021

Based on the table above, when watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv, respondents tend to be unable to escape from problems. This is evident from the number of respondents who choose the category of “not getting and not getting” which when added up is 68%. So it can be concluded that variety shows and reality shows on Transtv tend not to be able to escape the respondents from the problems they are experiencing.

Correlation Test Results

The following will prove how strong the relationship between motives and satisfaction with watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv is through television.

From the calculation results, the first output table “-none-a” shows the correlation value between the motivation variable and satisfaction before the inclusion of the controlling variable “intensity” into the analysis. From this output, it is known that the correlation coefficient (Correlations) is 0.517 (positive) and the significance value (2-tailed) is 0.00, so it can be concluded that there is a positive

and significant relationship between motivation and satisfaction without the control variable (intensity). While the Correlations value of 0.517 is included in the category of strong relationship.

In the second output table "SQRT_Intensitas" shows the correlation value between the Motivation variable and Satisfaction after entering Intensity as a control variable into the analysis. From this output table, it can be seen that there is a decrease in the value of the correlation coefficient (Correlations) to 0.352 (still positive but in the category of weak relationship) and the Significance (2-tailed-) value of $0.013 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that the relationship between motive and satisfaction with watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv with watching intensity as a control variable is significant (significant). So it can be concluded that the intensity of students when watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv through television media as a controlling variable will have an influence on the relationship between motivation to watch variety shows and reality shows on Transtv and satisfaction when watching variety shows and reality shows on Transtv.

Table 7. Partial correlation: Entertainment motive as independent variable. Entertainment satisfaction as dependent variable and intensity as intervening variable
Correlations

Control Variables			SQRT_Motif	SQRT_Kepuasan	SQRT_Inensitas
-none ^a	SQRT_Motif	Correlation	1.000	.517	.460
		Significance (2-tailed)	.	.000	.001
		Df	0	48	48
	SQRT_Kepuasan	Correlation	.517	1.000	.559
		Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000
		Df	48	0	48
	SQRT_Inensitas	Correlation	.460	.559	1.000
		Significance (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.
		Df	48	48	0
SQRT_Inensitas	SQRT_Motif	Correlation	1.000	.352	
		Significance (2-tailed)	.	.013	
		Df	0	47	
	SQRT_Kepuasan	Correlation	.352	1.000	
		Significance (2-tailed)	.013	.	
		Df	47	0	

a. Cells contain zero-order (Pearson) correlations.

Source: Primary data processed by researchers, 2021

Conclusion

The results of the research that have been carried out explain that the relationship between motive and satisfaction affects the intensity of watching. The high desire of respondents to watch a program, encourages psychologically to use the media. If the motivation of the respondent is high, the intensity of watching is also more intense and the level of satisfaction of the respondent also increases. So it can be said that the results of the partial correlation test in this study can prove the existence of the

uses and gratification theory, where a person's social and psychological origin for media needs produces a strong motive to encourage audiences to use media as a means to fulfill their needs.

The intensity of watching variety shows and reality shows on TransTV is also inseparable from the content that is broadcast. Therefore, it would be better if TransTV could show content that is entertaining but still contains education and information so that apart from being entertaining, it can also have a positive impact on the audience.

References

- Bidzilya, Y. M., Haladzhun, Z. V., Georgiievskaya, V. V., Solomin, Y. O., & Sydorenko, N. M. (2021). Ukrainian communication and media in Romania. *Linguistics and Culture Review*, 5(S4). <https://doi.org/10.21744/lingcure.v5ns4.1576>
- Campo-Prieto, P., Cancela, J. M., & Rodríguez-Fuentes, G. (2021). Immersive virtual reality as physical therapy in older adults: present or future (systematic review). *Virtual Reality*, 25(3). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10055-020-00495-x>
- Chen, Y., & Liu, X. (2021). 5W Mode Analysis of the Media Communication Strategies of Online Video-Produced Variety Shows Using the Chinese Variety Show U Can U BiBi as an Example. *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, 1191 AISC. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49889-4_56
- Dixon, M., Bergin, H., A'Court, S., Shea, K., & Kim, E. J. (Jenny). (2021). The surgical rotation program - "Surgical swapsies". *Australian Nursing & Midwifery Journal*, 27(5).
- Fardiah, D., Darmawan, F., & Rinawati, R. (2020). Media literacy capabilities of broadcast monitoring in regional Indonesian broadcasting commission (KPID) of West Java. *Jurnal Komunikasi: Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 36(4). <https://doi.org/10.17576/JKMJC-2020-3604-08>
- Farmer, R. (2016). Cinema advertising and the Sea Witch 'Lost Island' film (1965). *Historical Journal of Film, Radio and Television*, 36(4). <https://doi.org/10.1080/01439685.2015.1129709>
- Kuzina, G. (2020). The concept of a digital transformation of a traditional university to a "digital university." *E-Management*, 3(2). <https://doi.org/10.26425/2658-3445-2020-2-89-96>
- Kwon, Y. C., Jang, J. W., Lim, H., & Choi, O. (2020). Feasibility analysis of deep learning-based reality assessment of human back-view images. *Electronics (Switzerland)*, 9(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics9040656>
- Littlejohn, S. W., Foss, K. A., & Oetzel, J. G. (2017). Theories of Humas Communication. In *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling* (Vol. 53, Issue 9).
- Lu, S., & Lu, S. (2022). A Postmodern Analysis of Intralingual Subtitles in China's Web-Only Variety Shows: A Case of Mars Intelligence Agency. *International Journal of Communication*, 16.
- M, M., K, N., N, B., & DR, R. (2018). Teenagers Understanding and Influence of Media Content on their Diet and Health- Related Behaviour. *Journal of Clinical Nutrition & Dietetics*, 04(02). <https://doi.org/10.4172/2472-1921.100071>
- Makarov, P., Makarova, T., Samoylenko, Z., Gulakova, N., & Kravchenko, I. (2022). PRODUCTIVITY AND QUALITY EVALUATION OF TARRAGON AND THYME GROWN UNDER ARTIFICIAL LIGHT. *Vestnik of Kazan State Agrarian University*, 16(4). <https://doi.org/10.12737/2073-0462-2022-24-29>
- Prati, E. (2020). From the west to the Kremlin and back: The development paths of Foreign products on Russian television. *Comunicazioni Sociali*, 2. https://doi.org/10.26350/001200_000082
- Publication, I. (2021). AN ANALYSIS OF "LIMITED AND SELECTIVE EFFECT THEORY" AND "USES AND GRATIFICATION THEORY" FROM PERSPECTIVE OF MASS MEDIA RESEARCH. *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 12(4).
- Roberts, J., & De Benedictis, S. (2021). Childbirth on television: a scoping review and recommendations for further research. *Feminist Media Studies*, 21(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/14680777.2019.1690025>
- Sukardi, I. (2016). Character Education Based on Religious Values: an Islamic Perspective. *Ta'dib*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.19109/td.v21i1.744>
- Woo, K. H., & Khoo, S. L. (2020). Ecology and new urban program: A case study of Penang state own brand of affordable housing program. *Journal of Urban Management*, 9(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jum.2020.01.001>
- Wuethrich, S., Hannula, D. E., Mast, F. W., & Henke, K. (2018). Subliminal encoding and flexible retrieval of objects in scenes. *Hippocampus*, 28(9). <https://doi.org/10.1002/hipo.22957>
- Yakunin, K., Kalimoldayev, M., Mukhamediev, R. I., Mussabayev, R., Barakhnin, V., Kuchin, Y., Murzakhmetov, S., Buldybayev, T., Ospanova, U., Yelis, M., Zhumabayev, A., Gopejenko, V., Meirambekyzy, Z., & Abdurazakov, A. (2021). Kaznewsdataset: Single country overall digital mass media publication corpus. *Data*, 6(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/data6030031>